

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE MICROSCALE IMPREGNATION IN COMMINGLED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE YARNS

R. Gennaro, A. Greco, F. Lionetto, A. Maffezzoli
Department of Innovation Engineering, University of Salento
Via Monteroni, 73100 Lecce
alfonso.maffezzoli@unisalento.it

SUMMARY

Through thickness impregnation of a glass woven fabric with an amorphous polyethylene-terephthalate (PETG) matrix was studied combining compression moulding experiments with a finite element model for intra-bundle matrix flow. The non-Newtonian rheological behaviour of the thermoplastic matrix was used to predict the tow permeability of an array of randomly spaced and non-overlapping unidirectional fibers. The model was used to obtain macroscopic permeability and the results were compared with Carman-Kozeny equation as well as with thickness changes during compression moulding. Experimental data indicated the existence of inter-bundle and intra-bundle flow well separated in the time scale.

Keywords: tow permeability, thermoplastic matrix composites, amorphous PET, compression molding, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Commingled yarn semi-pregs, or stackings of thermoplastic films and dry reinforcements, are attracting growing interest in the manufacturing of thermoplastic composites, mainly because they can lead to fast processing of composites by compression moulding [1-4]. During the forming process, the material is initially conformed to the lower part of the mould and then, during heat and pressure application, a microscopic flow of matrix wets out the fibres. The impregnation process is strongly affected by the reinforcement permeability, whose knowledge is essential for controlling the fibre wetting and consequently, the quality of the composite part [5].

The measurement of the permeability in thermoplastic semi-pregs is not straightforward, since thousands of fiber filaments within a tow are randomly distributed and very tightly packed. The reinforcement presents a dual porosity because the spacing between the tows is usually an order of magnitude higher than fibre spacing inside the tows. Accordingly, the inter-bundle and intra-bundle permeabilities are different by orders of magnitude [6-7] leading to a polymer flow through semi-pregs,

which involves macroflow around a fiber bundle and microflow within the fiber bundle. Therefore, prediction of permeability of fibrous reinforcements represents a crucial requirement for the design and the optimization of manufacturing processes of composites involving fibre impregnation.

The permeability of fibrous media varies substantially with the fibre volume fraction, and it is usually predicted based on the theoretical models developed for flow through porous media using the classical theory of Darcy's law[7-8]. Several models have been developed to predict the permeability of fibrous media in liquid composite moulding processes involving thermosetting resins [9-13] but very few on commingled yarn composites [14]. Some of them concern micro and macro impregnation, but they only consider the in plane permeability, where the impregnation flow is parallel to the plane of reinforcement layers.

Nevertheless, during compression moulding of thermoplastic matrix composites, the flow is perpendicular to the plane of reinforcement layers. Therefore, the knowledge of transversal permeability, both inter-bundle and intra-bundle, is essential for the correct simulation of the matrix flow and process optimization [15-17]. To the best of our knowledge, very few papers account for transversal permeability and no works deal with the microscale impregnation considering a non-Newtonian behaviour of the matrix. Even if very low velocity are encountered during bundle impregnation, high shearing is experienced by the matrix being the flow through channels of average dimensions comparable to fibre diameter.

In this work, numerical simulations of the transversal permeability of amorphous PET and glass fibers are presented assuming a non-Newtonian behaviour of the matrix. The model results are interpreted in terms of permeability and compared with experimental results obtained by compression moulding.

EXPERIMENTAL

The material used is amorphous PET copolymer (PETG), provided by Embrace Shrink Film from Eastman, with an intrinsic viscosity of 0.70 dl/g, and density of 1.30 g/cm³. The glass fiber reinforcement is a bidirectional unbalanced 90/10 fabric, EE425 provided by SEAL (Italy), with a nominal thickness of 0.26 mm, and a nominal weight of 425 g/m².

The experimental measurements of consolidation were carried out on samples made of two layers of glass fabric and one layer of PETG film, 150 microns thick. The nominal fiber volume content of the sample was 42.3 %. The PET film were obtained by compression moulding with a Campana PL71 press at 220°C and 70 bar pressure. The rheological characterization of PETG was performed, with a strain-controlled rheometer (ARES, TA Instrument, USA) equipped with a cone and plate geometry (25 mm diameter). Five isothermal experiments between 180 °C and 250 °C were performed. The strain rate was varied between 0.1 s⁻¹ and 10 s⁻¹.

Through thickness impregnation experiments were performed on a LLOYD LR5K dynamometer at constant temperature, 235°C, and using laminates of 200 mm diameter. Tests have been carried out at a constant compression load of 1800 N, corresponding to a pressure of 0.1 MPa.

Fibre content of specimen was determined by resin burn out tests and used for evaluation of the theoretical density of the composite. Five specimens were cut from the consolidated composite at different distances from the disk center. The average value and uniformity of fiber content was evaluated. The fiber weight fraction was 60.3 ± 3.04 , which evidences a reasonably uniform distribution of fibers in the composite.

Morphology of samples was studied by optical microscopy (Nikon Model Epiphot 200) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (EVO 60 ZEISS).

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Glass bundles were modelled by a random distribution of long cylindrical fibres, with axes aligned perpendicularly to the direction of bulk flow, and cross sections randomly placed in the x-y plane. A sketch of one of several control volumes used for the numerical simulations is reported in Fig. 1a. It includes 350 parallel non-overlapping fibers (14 microns diameter) in a 35.3×35.3 mm square domain with a fiber volume fraction $V_f = 0.4323$. Fibres were placed in different configurations using a subroutine for the random generation of numbers written with Matlab 6.5 (MathWorks Inc., USA). The program includes a non overlapping condition and provides as output a file that contains the geometry to be used in fluid dynamics simulations (Fig. 1a). The flow direction along the y axis is from top to bottom.

The flow of the polymer melt across the interstitial spaces of the porous medium is driven by a constant pressure gradient in the y direction. The pressure was varied between 0.1 and 3 MPa, which represent typical values used in composite manufacturing. The governing equations of the flow are given by a system of continuity and momentum equations:

$$\begin{cases} \rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} - \rho (\vec{u} \bullet \nabla) \vec{u} + \nabla p + \nabla \bullet \tau = \vec{f} \\ \nabla \bullet \vec{u} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau = 2\mu \left(\dot{\gamma} \right) \frac{1}{2} \left(\nabla \vec{u} + (\nabla \vec{u})^T \right) \quad (2)$$

where \vec{u} is the velocity vector, p the pressure, ρ and η the fluid density and viscosity, respectively.

The system of flow equations was solved assuming a simple power law constitutive equation to describe the non-Newtonian behaviour of the thermoplastic matrix:

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = m * \dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \quad (3)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate, m and n are model parameters. When considering the case of Newtonian flow, n has been set equal to 1.

The finite element (FE) solutions were obtained by using the Comsol Multiphysics software (version 3.5, Comsol AB, Sweden). The model equations were solved with their associated boundary conditions:

- no-slip at solid fiber boundaries, i.e. the velocities are zero on the fiber surfaces;
- slip-symmetry at the left and right exterior boundaries, i.e. the normal velocities gradients are zero along the planes of symmetry;
- normal/flow pressure at the upper boundary (inflow) with a pressure ranging from 0.1 to 3 MPa;
- normal/flow pressure at the lower boundary (outflow) with a pressure of 0 Pa.

Figure 1: a) Representative volume for unidirectional disordered fiber arrays (350 fibers, $V_f=0.432$); b) Viscosity plot of gPET.

RESULTS

Rheological characterization of the thermoplastic matrix

The rheological behaviour of molten PETG is non Newtonian, as showed in Fig. 1b. At different temperatures, different values for m and n were found by power law fitting of experimental viscosity curves. The values of m and n are reported in Table I. As it can be observed, m decreases and n increases with increasing temperature.

Table I: Regression parameters for PETG viscosity curves at different temperatures.

Temperature [°C]	m	n
180	5370	0.62
200	2162	0.66
210	794	0.87
220	489	0.81
250	154	0.85

Model definition

At the beginning, the computational work was focused on defining the most appropriate geometric domain for the representation of the random dispersion of perfectly aligned unidirectional fibers in the thermoplastic matrix. As demonstrated by Chen and Papathanasiou [17], the permeability data are affected by a high scattering due to the stochastic nature of the fiber distribution. In order to reduce this scattering and choose the most representative domain, the number of random distributions (N_{rd}) and the number of fibers (N_f) was optimized, keeping constant the fiber volume fraction ($V_f=0.423$).

First of all, several random distributions were generated and the velocity field through those domains was simulated. For these simulations a low number of fibres ($N_f=50$) was adopted. The effect of the number of random distributions (N_{rd}) on the average velocity is reported in Fig. 2a. The low number of fibers used for the simulation is expected to increase the effect of the domain external boundaries and thus the scattering in the computed velocity field. The average velocities converged towards a plateau at $N_{rd}=32$. For higher number of simulations the differences in the computed average velocities were lower than 3%.

Figure 2: a) Effect of the number of random distributions (N_r) on the average velocity simulated with a pressure gradient of 1 MPa; b) Effect of the fiber number (N_f) on the average velocity. The error bars indicate the standard deviations.

Afterwards, the number of fibers (N_f) was changed to check the minimum number capable to give a stable solution. Models with different N_f (ranging from 50 to 500 fibers) were generated and 32 simulation were run for each of them. The effect of the number of fibers (N_f) on the average velocity is reported in Fig. 2b. For comparison purposes, the average velocity as a function of N_f is also shown in Fig. 2a for a Newtonian behaviour assuming a constant viscosity of $2162\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$. The average values of velocity and their scattering decreased with increasing N_f . After $N_f=350$, a plateau value was attained. Also, for $N_f > 300$ the standard deviation of average velocities is significantly reduced, which indicates a lower effect of fiber distribution in the domain on the average velocity. Also, as it can be observed, most of the error in the simulation

is due to the non-Newtonian behaviour of the matrix. In facts, the standard deviation of the average velocity is much lower for Newtonian simulation, and the plateau value is attained for $N_f=150$. Therefore, $N_f=350$ and $N_{rd}=32$ were assumed for the simulation of intra-bundle flow. A similar approach was already proposed for the permeability calculation of composites [17] and nanocomposites for barrier applications [5].

Transversal permeability determination

Simulations were performed for pressure ranging from 0.1 to 3 MPa, in order to calculate the permeability, K_y , in the y direction, for a non-Newtonian fluid. For each pressure value, 32 simulations at $N_f=350$ were run. In the case of Newtonian flow, the velocity field is integrated to give the total flow rate Q . The permeability K of the fibrous medium is then calculated according to the Darcy's law:

$$v = K \frac{\Delta P}{\eta_0 L} \quad (4)$$

where η is the fluid viscosity, ΔP the pressure drop and L is the thickness of the fibrous medium.

The Darcy's law relates linearly the fluid velocity to the pressure gradient by the matrix viscosity and the permeability of porous medium. Nevertheless, thermoplastic matrix are usually non-Newtonian fluids, which yields a non linear relation between average velocity and pressure. This suggests that a modification of the Darcy's law must be applied to the case of non-Newtonian flow. The pressure dependence of the computed velocity values can be fitted by a binomial equation in the following form:

$$v = \Delta P(a_1 + a_2 \Delta P) \quad (5)$$

Using a pressure dependent permeability $K=K_1+K_2*\Delta P$, the Darcy's equation can be modified as following:

$$v = \frac{\Delta P}{mL} (K_1 + K_2 \Delta P) \quad (6)$$

By comparison of eq (5) and eq. (6) the permeability coefficients can be obtained as:

$$K_i = a_i \frac{\Delta P}{mL} \quad i=1, 2 \quad (7)$$

In this work, the values of a_1 and a_2 were obtained by polynomial fitting of experimental data according to eq. (5). Afterwards, the values of the permeability coefficients were obtained from eq. (7).

The obtained K values refer to the transversal permeability because the flow is perpendicular to the plain of the reinforcement layers.

Compression moulding experiments

Isothermal consolidation experiments were performed at a pressure of 0.1 MPa and a temperature of 235°C. By compression tests, the evolution of sample thickness δ as a

function of time is obtained. Afterwards, the composite density can be obtained assuming that the sample mass M and the in plane dimension of the composite A are constant:

$$\rho(t) = \frac{M}{A * \delta(t)} \quad (8)$$

By knowledge of the theoretical density ρ_t , the experimental void content of the composite X_{ve} can be calculated as:

$$X_{ve} = 1 - \frac{\rho(t)}{\rho_t} \quad (9)$$

The theoretical density, for a fiber weight fraction of 60.3%, was calculated to be 1.78 g/cm³.

The void fraction can be related to the velocity field, and thus to the permeability, by using the scheme reported in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Scheme to relate the void fraction to the velocity field.

The void fraction is obtained by the melt front x_f as:

$$X_{vf} = X_{v,0} - \frac{x_f}{s} X_{v,0} = X_{v,0} \left(1 - \frac{x_f}{s} \right) \quad (8)$$

where $X_{v,0}$ is the initial void fraction. The melt front can be obtained by solution of the Darcy law in its differential form:

$$\frac{\partial x_f}{\partial t} = k \frac{\Delta P}{x_f} \Rightarrow x_f = \sqrt{2K\Delta P t} \quad (9)$$

By combining eq. (8) and eq. (9), the simulated void fraction as a function of time can be obtained as:

$$X_{vf} = X_{v,0} \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2K\Delta P}}{s} \sqrt{t} \right) \quad (10)$$

A plot of X_{ve} as a function of $t^{0.5}$, shown in Fig. 4, presents two linear behaviour zones. This evidences that the model developed and reported in eq. (10) is suitable to represent the consolidation of composite in film stacking.

Figure 4: A plot of X_{ve} as a function of $t^{0.5}$.

The first slope in Fig. 4 provides a $K_{exp1}=5.9 \text{ E-}10 \text{ m}^2$ while for the second slope $K_{exp2} = 5.63\text{E-}11 \text{ m}^2$ was calculated.

The experimental K values can be compared with those calculated applying the Carman Kozeny equation, assuming $k_0=60$:

$$K = \frac{d_f^2}{16k_0} \times \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (11)$$

Assuming $d_f= 0.6 \text{ mm}$ as the average bundle diameter, a value of $K = 3.25\text{E-}10 \text{ m}^2$ is obtained. This value is very close to the value obtained from fitting of the first zone of Fig. 4, which evidences that the first void fraction decrease can be attributed to inter-bundle impregnation, being associated to a relatively high permeability.

On the other hand, taking $d_f=14 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ as the fiber diameter, a value of $K=5.92\text{E-}13 \text{ m}^2$ is obtained from Carman Kozeny equation, which is much lower than the value obtained from linear fitting of the second zone of Fig. 4. Furthermore, the simulation at 0.1 MPa , assuming a non-Newtonian behavior, leads to $K= 1.00 \text{ E-}12 \text{ m}^2$, which is comparable to the value obtained from Carman Kozeny equation, and 50 times lower than K_{exp2} . These results indicate that the second void fraction reduction zone is due to intra-impregnation, which is associated to a much lower permeability.

The reason for the poor estimate of experimental data by numerical simulation can be better understood by looking at the micrographs reported in Fig. 5. As it can be observed, the unbalanced fabric has a much higher fiber content in the warp direction. As a consequence, the fibers aligned along the warp direction are weakly impregnated. On the other hand, the low content of fibers in the weft direction allows efficient impregnation of the fibers, as observed in Fig. 5. The numerical simulation could be related to the impregnation of fibers in the warp direction, and leads to a very low permeability compared to the permeability in the weft direction. The experimental data, and in particular the second zone of void reduction, are instead relative to the impregnation of the fibers in the weft direction, associated to an higher permeability than the one calculated in the warp direction.

Figure 5: Fiber impregnation in weft and warp direction.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a model for the transversal permeability of fibrous media has been developed. The model accounts for the stochastic nature and variability of the fiber distribution. The model has been compared with experimental data obtained from consolidation tests on PETG and glass fibers. Experimental data have shown that probably the glass fiber impregnation is a two step process, the first one involving inter-bundle impregnation, the second one intra-bundle impregnation. Further differences can arise due to different fiber content in the warp and weft direction. The simulation model developed is, at the moment, not capable to capture the different mechanisms involved in fiber impregnation. On the other hand, the generic nature of the model proposed can be used to tailor the numerical simulation to different processing conditions, including the effect of inter and intra-bundle as well as the effect of different fiber content in different directions. Further studies are in progress to analyse the effect of the fiber volume fraction on the tow permeability and the experimental validation with K measurements. Furthermore, the research will be extended to different reinforcement types in order to generalize the results.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was funded by the regional project INCOR

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